

The Influence of the Collaborative Learning Model on the Achievement of Class X Students at SMA Angkasa 1 Halim Perdanakusuma Jakarta

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to determine the effect of the collaborative learning model on the achievement of class X students at SMA Angkasa 1 Halim Perdanakusuma Jakarta FY 2022/2023. The research design used in this research is True-Experimental Design. The sampling technique used is purposive sampling namely a sampling technique with certain considerations. So the classes used as samples in this research were class X.1 as the experimental class and class X.2 as the control class. Based on statistical analysis the research results show t_{count} of 20.59 is greater than t_{table} of 2.02. So it can be concluded that there is an influence of collaborative learning on the achievement of class X students at SMA Angkasa 1 Halim Perdanakusuma Jakarta.

Keywords: Collaborative Learning, Student achievement, Student's motivation to study

INTRODUCTION

Collaborative learning requires a modification of learning objectives from simply conveying information to constructing knowledge by individuals through group learning. In collaborative learning there are no different tasks for each individual, but rather the tasks belong together and are completed together without differentiating between students' learning conversations. With collaboration, students can learn to deliberate, students learn to respect other people's opinions, can develop critical and rational thinking, can foster a sense of cooperation, healthy competition. (Hosnan, 2014:318).

The reality in the field shows that there are still many teachers who use learning methods that do not improve Active student participation makes learning monotonous and boring for students. As a result, the learning outcomes achieved by students are not optimal and some are even below the minimum learning completeness criteria. This also happens in chemistry learning at school. Many students feel bored because the teacher only uses the lecture method so that students are unable to understand the material being presented. Obstacles to the learning process include the lack of educator participation in implementing various strategies that are relevant to classroom situations, and the evaluation system has no dimensions diagnostics to find the causes of students' difficulty understanding learning at school. The above phenomenon is a manifestation of the gap that has occurred between the educational goals to be achieved and the abilities expected of students.

From this description, it turns out that the cause of the gap could come from the students or educators themselves. Whether students are interested in the lessons delivered by educators is one of the causes of students' weakness in remembering lessons. Furthermore, the obstacle that students often face is that teachers do not give students the opportunity to be creative in completing learning tasks. So students are unable to develop their creativity in solving new problems given by educators. So this causes problems during the learning process, for example students get bored during the learning process, students do not focus on the material taught by the teacher, play in class during learning, students are not active during the discussion process, less active in asking if there is material that is missing. not yet understood and there are many other examples. These problems cause low student learning outcomes. Therefore, as an educator, you must be clever in choosing the methods or models used during the learning process.

Choosing a model or learning method is a solution to problems related to the success of the teaching

and learning process. The appropriate model that can foster student activity in class is the collaborative learning model which can be formulated as one learning model that can develop students' active participation. Collaborative learning has three general characteristics, namely a change in the relationship between teachers and students, a new approach to teaching by teachers, and the composition of collaborative learning. Learning, between teachers and students sharing experiences that can be used as knowledge in the learning that will be carried out. Teachers and students share authority and the formation of heterogeneous student groups (Gokhale, 1995). Collaborative goal structures are characterized by a large amount of interdependence between students in the group.

Ruseffendy (in Purniati et al, 2009:3) states that using appropriate learning techniques and methods allows students to learn more actively, because they suit the students' learning styles. Apart from that, a learning model is also needed that attracts students' interest in studying the material presented by the teacher, so that learning can run effectively. Vygotsky (in Santrock, 2008:62) states that knowledge is distributed between people and the environment, which includes objects, artifacts, tools, books, and the communities where people live. This shows that acquiring knowledge can best be achieved through interaction with other people in joint activities. Vygotsky (1986) views that knowledge is constructed collaboratively between individuals and this situation can be adjusted by each individual. One learning model that can be used is the collaborative learning model.

The collaborative learning model is a learning model where students work together in small groups to achieve understanding and learning goals. Collaborative learning (collaborative learning) is a term (umbrella term) which includes many forms of collaborative learning, from small group projects to more specific forms of group work called cooperative learning (Noble dkk, 2005).

Collaborative learning is a form of constructivist learning that can improve team working skills and communication skills in groups during the teaching and learning process. Because through collaborative learning students can interact to solve tasks and mutually generate effective problem solving strategies in their respective proximal development (zone of proximal development) they. According to Vygotsky (in Santrock, 2007:62) zone of proximal development is a series of tasks that are too difficult for a child to master alone but can be learned with help from adults or more capable children. Collaborative learning models are expected to accommodate students to learn to communicate and work together well. Collaborative learning is an alternative learning that can improve student learning processes and outcomes.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research aims to determine the effect of the collaborative learning model on the achievement of class X students at SMA Angkasa 1 Halim Perdanakusuma Jakarta FY 2022/2023. The research design used in this research is True-Experimental Design. The sampling technique used is purposive sampling namely a sampling technique with certain considerations. So the classes used as samples in this research were class X.1 as the experimental class and class X.2 as the control class. Based on statistical analysis the research results show t_{count} of 20.59 is greater than t_{table} of 2.02. So it can be concluded that there is an influence of collaborative learning on the achievement of class X students at SMA Angkasa 1 Halim Perdanakusuma Jakarta.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the results of observations carried out by researchers in the field to measure the influence of parenting patterns and the learning environment on students' learning motivation, data was obtained which were collected using a questionnaire with the following description:

Table 1. Deskriptif statistik
From : Researcher Data

Variable	N	min	max	mean	Std dev
Parenting	141	33	49	41,05	2,649
Learning Environment	141	40	55	47,59	2,940
Students Motivations	141	30	44	38,07	2,892
Valid N	141				

Test analysis requirements

Analysis prerequisite tests are a form of test requirements that must be fulfilled first before

proceeding to the next analysis stage (Sugiyono & Susanto, 2017). In this research, prerequisite tests were carried out including normality test, heteroscedasticity test, and multicollinearity test.

Normality test

The normality test is carried out to find out whether the data used in the research is normally distributed or not normally distributed. From the test results one sample K-S carried out, the following results were obtained:

Table 2. *one sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test*
From : Researcher Data

N		141
Normal parameter	Mean	0,000000
	Std. Deviation	2,70626167
Most extreme	Absolute	0,063
Differences	Positive	0,032
	Negative	-0,63
Test statistic		0,063
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0,200 ^{c,d}

From the normality test results above, the asymp sig (2-tailed) value is 0.200, which is greater than 0.05. Sugiyono & Susanto (2017) explained that data is declared to have a normal distribution if the Asymp Sig (2-tailed) value is > 0.05.

Normality test results can also be seen in the histogram and graph below:

Figure 1. Histogram Grafik

Table 3. Coefisient

Model	Unstandarized coefficient		Standarized coefficient beta	t	Sig.
	B	Std. error			
(constan)	21,290	4,865		4,505	,000
Pola Asuh	-0,010	0,088	-0,010	-0,119	,906
Lingkungan Belajar	0,348	0,079	0,354	4,409	,000

a. dependent variable: motivasi belajar

Heteroscedasticity test

The heteroscedasticity test is carried out to determine whether the data used is homogeneous or heterogeneous. This aims to find out whether in the regression model there are differences between one residual observation and another residual observation. A good regression model is a model that is homoscedastic or the data used must be homogeneous or harmonious. Based on the test results carried out by the researchers, the results of the heteroscedasticity test were obtained in the following scatter plot graph:

The scatterplot graph in Figure 3 above shows that there is no particular pattern and the points are spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis, so it can be said that heteroscedasticity does not occur.

Multicollinearity test

The multicollinearity test aims to test whether the regression model finds a correlation between independent variables. A good regression model should have no correlation between independent variables. The multicollinearity test in this study is presented in the following table:

Table 4. multicollinearity test

Model	Collinearity statistic	
	Tolerance	VIF
(constan)		
Pola Asuh (X1)	0,984	1,017
Lingkungan belajar (X2)	0,984	1,017

a. dependen variabel : motivasi belajar siswa

Multicollinearity test results in Figure 4.5. above shows that all variables have a tolerance value > 0.1 ($0.984 > 0.1$) and $VIF < 10$ ($1.017 < 10$). This means that all variables are free from multicollinearity problems (non-multicollinearity).

Regression analysis

The multiple regression test in this research was carried out to test the hypothesis. Based on the multiple regression estimates, results were obtained as shown in the following table:

$$Y = 21,920 - 0,010X1 + 0,348X2 + 0,05$$

Note:

Y = Learning Motivasion Variable

X1 = Parenting Variable

X2 = Environment Learning

e = alpha

Correlation coefficient analysis

Correlation analysis is used to measure the strength of the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Correlation analysis is presented in the following figure:

Table 4. model summary of correlation analysis (b)

Model	R	R squared	Adjusted R square	Std error of the estimate
1	0,353 ^a	0,125	0,112	2,726

a. Predictors: (Constant), parenting, environmet Learning
b. Dependent Variable: Learning Motivation

Analysis of the coefficient of determination

The coefficient of determination is used to determine the contribution of the independent variable to the dependent variable which is presented as follows:

Table 5. model summary of correlation analysis (b)

Model	R	R squared	Adjusted R square	Std error of the estimate
1	0,353 ^a	0,125	0,112	2,726

a. Predictors: (Constant), parenting, environmet Learning
b. Dependent Variable: Learning Motivation

Partial hypothesis test (t test)

The t test is used to determine the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable partially, which is presented as follows:

Table 6. coeficient

Model	Unstandarized coefficient		Standarized coefficient beta	t	Sig.
	B	Std.error			
(constan)	21,290	4,865		4,505	,000
Parenting	-0,010	0,088	-0,010	-0,119	,906
environmet Learning	0,348	0,079	0,354	4,409	,000

a. dependent variable: Learning Motivation

To prove and find out whether the independent variables have a simultaneous influence on the dependent variable, an F test is carried out. Or this f test is to find out whether the work culture and teamwork together they influence employee performance. If $p < 0.05$, in other words, the F significance value is smaller than 5%, so the regression model is statistically significant.

Uji hipotesis simultan (ujif)

Uji f dilakukan untuk mengetahui apakah variabel x1 dan x2 secara bersama-sama memberikan pengaruh terhadap variabel Y. Hasil uji F dalam penelitian ini disajikan sebagai berikut:

Table 7. Annova

Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	f	Sig.
Regression	145,951	2	72,976	9,822	,000 ^b
Residual	1025,339	138	7,430		
Total	1171,291	140			

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Motivation
b. Predictors: (Constant), parenting, environmet Learning

To prove and find out whether the independent variables have a simultaneous influence on the dependent variable, an F test is carried out. Or this f test is to find out whether the work culture and teamwork together they influence employee performance. $p < 0.05$, in other words, the F significance value is smaller than 5%, so the regression model is statistically significant.

CONCLUSION

1. Regression analysis

From the coefficient table above, the regression equation value is obtained as follows:

$$Y = 21,920 - 0,010x_1 + 0,348x_2$$

- A constant value of 21.920 means that if the parenting pattern and learning environment variables are at point 0 (zero) then the learning motivation variable is at 21.920 units.
- The b_{1x1} value of -0.010 means that if there is an increase in parenting patterns by one unit, it will result in a decrease in learning motivation provided that other variables remain the same or do not change, a negative regression value that is not in the same direction means that the relationship is not in the same direction.
- The b_{2x2} value of 0.348 means that if there is an increase in the learning environment variable by one unit, it will provide an increase in student learning motivation of 0.348 units provided that other variables remain constant or do not change.

2. Correlation analysis

From table 5 of the correlation analysis summary model (b) above, you can see that the R value is 0.353, explaining that variables X1 and X2 have a correlation value of 0.353, which shows that the two independent variables have a weak but meaningful correlation or relationship.

3. Analysis of the coefficient of determination

From table 5 of the correlation analysis summary model (b) above, it can be seen that the value of the coefficient of determination (Adjusted R Square) for multiple regression between the independent variable and the dependent variable is 0.122. This value shows that parenting style and the learning environment together contribute 12.2% to student learning motivation and the remaining 87.8% is influenced by other factors on employee performance but were not included in this research.

4. Partial hypothesis test

a. Test hypothesis 1

From the coefficient table, the calculated t value is -0.119 which is smaller than the t table of 141;0.05, namely 1.65573 ($-0.119 < 1.65573$) and the sig value is greater than 0.05 ($0.906 > 0.05$), meaning that the hypothesis regarding the influence of parenting styles on student learning outcomes is rejected. The relevant research results (Rini Harianti and Suci Amin), 2016. This research was carried out at the Smart Tampan Pekanbaru School. The sample consisted of 57 smart school students at Tampan Pekanbaru. The approach taken in this research is qualitative and quantitative. The results show that parenting patterns are positive in terms of parental control (64%), clarity of communication (61%) and mature parental demands (54%). Students have positive internal (68%) and external (55%) motivation in learning. There is a significant and positive influence between parenting styles on students' learning motivation with a significant value of 0.000 with a coefficient of determination of 69.1%. It was concluded that parenting styles influence students' learning motivation. It is recommended that parents and schools implement good parenting patterns, create learning situations that can stimulate students' interest in studying actively and pay attention to their children's school needs.

b. Test hypothesis 2

In the coefficient table, the calculated t value is 4.409 which is greater than the t table of 141;0.05, namely 1.65573 ($4.409 > 1.65573$) and the sig value which is smaller than 0.05 is 0.000 ($0.000 < 0.05$) from these results, hypothesis 2 which states that it is suspected that there is an influence between the learning environment on student learning motivation is accepted. There are relevant research results (Elis Wartti), 2016. This research aims to determine the influence of student learning motivation at the Angkasa 10 Halim Perdana Kusuma Elementary School, East Jakarta. The hypothesis that will be tested is that there is a positive influence between learning motivation and mathematics learning outcomes. This research was conducted using a survey method, with a target population of all class VI students at Angkasa 10 Halim Perdanakusuma Elementary School. Samples taken at simple random. The research instruments that will be used are lift distribution and mathematics learning tests. To measure motivation, an attitude scale test is used which is based on content validation. Reliability is calculated using the Cronbach's alpha formula. The learning outcomes test uses questions given in accordance with the current curriculum. Reliability is calculated using the normality test and homogeneity test followed by the t test (two-party test) which is significant at the 0.05 significance level. In the experimental group test, $Y = 0.0978$ and L table = 0.161 and X Lo = 0.0974). The results of the research concluded as follows: "There is a positive influence between student learning motivation and student mathematics learning outcomes. With the regression equation $Y = a + bx = 29.65 + 0.605x$. The correlation coefficient (r) = 0.974 is significant at 0.05. It is hoped that the results of this research will be useful for educators, especially mathematics teachers.

5. Simultaneous hypothesis testing

Simultaneous hypothesis testing is aimed at finding out whether there is a joint influence between the independent variables on the dependent variable. From the results of the analysis presented in the ANOVA table, the calculated f value is 9.882 which is greater than the calculated f of 141-df; 0.05, namely of 3.06 ($9.882 > 3.06$) and a significance value of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$) from these results, the hypothesis states that it is suspected that there is an influence between parenting style and the learning environment simultaneously on motivation student learning is accepted. There are relevant research results from (Megi Andeni, Neni Hermita and Zufriady). 2019. Learning motivation is an internal and external factor for students to make behavior changes. The aim of this

research is to determine the effect of learning motivation on student learning outcomes. This research was conducted on 132 elementary school students at SDN Gugus Inti I, Kunto Darussalam District, Rokan Hulu Regency in the social studies subject. The research that has been carried out has obtained a simple linear regression equation $Y = a + bx$ or $Y = 13,610 + 0.834x$, explaining that if it is assumed that student learning motivation is 0 (zero), it will not affect student learning outcomes by 13,610. If learning motivation has increased by one unit, this can affect student learning outcomes by 0.834. Meanwhile, the R square value (contribution) explains that learning motivation has a contribution of 0.624 or 62.4% and the rest is influenced by other variables.

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